

DESIGN CONSTRUCTION AND TESTING OF AN INCREMENTAL SHAFT ENCODER FOR MEASUREMENT OF ANGULAR VELOCITY OF A SHAFT

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ABSTRACT

An incremental shaft encoder has been designed and developed for measuring angular velocity of a shaft. The construction of the circuit was achieved using disc of a plastic materials with fifteen slots. Infrared light emitting diode, comparator, photo transistor (sensor), 555 timer, encoder, decoder, differentiator (control logic) and display. Bubble resolver was also included in the circuits to eliminate ± 1 counting error which is inherent in most digital device. The incremental shaft encoder designed and developed was able to measure maximum speed of 2500rpm and the corresponding frequency of 625Hz of a 12V dc motor after proper calibration in laboratory and testing. The circuit designed and developed is a prototype of an industrial incremental shaft encoder, which replace the imported incremental shaft encoders because of its reliability.

KEYWORD: Speed (rpm), Frequency (Hz), digital instrument

INTRODUCTION

Today in the field of electronic instrumentation measurement, digital electronic instruments are preferred instead of analogue instruments, the use of electronic instruments enhance accuracy of measurement, minimizes loading effect and reducing electrical noise (Efedua, 2002).

Incremental shaft encoder is used generally to monitor the speed of motors and generators shaft, this work utilized a practical arrangement of incremental shaft using opto-interrupt device(OID); opto-interrupt device is a device that combines light emitting diode (LED) and photo transistor in close proximity (Efedua, 2002). The OID shown in fig. 1 is a package configuration equally spaced slots around the disc which allow light from the light emitting diode to reach the photo sensor. The rotating disc attached to the shaft of a motor is usually non-conducting materials. If there are disc has 15 slots around the disc, the OID output is 15 pulses for each complete rotation of the disc. The set may be used to sense the change in angular position of a motor shaft or speed of the motor. For regular spaced slots in the disc, the angular interval between any slots may be $360/n$ degree (John, 2002). Thus if there are 15 slots for example, the slot are spaced 24° interval. This is the maximum angular displacement that can be detected. A count of total number of pulses thus relates the angular displacement of the shaft. If the motor speed is ω revolution per minutes or $\omega/60$ revolution per second, the frequency of the pulse may be expressed as

$$f = \frac{n\omega}{60} \quad (1)$$

Where n is the number of pulses (Thomas, 2001)

Fig. 1: Block diagram of an incremental shaft encoder

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Brief Description of the Instrument

The circuit of incremental shaft encoder uses an opto-interrupt, device (OID) that combines light emitting diode and photo transistor in close proximity, the disc with 15 slots is attached to the shaft of the dc motor.

Schmitt trigger consist of comparator UA741 is connected to the emitter of the photo transistor and output of the Schmitt trigger is also connected to the binary counters for digital display as shown in Fig.1

Analysis of results

The results in Table 1, is plotted on the graph to establish the correlation between the frequency (Hz) and speed (rpm).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Slope} &= \frac{\text{Change in frequency}(rpm)}{\text{Change in frequency}} \\ &= \frac{2000 - 800}{500 - 200} \\ &= 4rpm/Hz \end{aligned}$$

Component Design

The design used an opto-interrupt device that combines light emitting diode and phototransistor in close proximity. An infrared light emitting diode emits light with a operating current of

$$I_d = \frac{V_{cc} - V_d}{R_1} \quad (2)$$

Where I_d and V_d are diode current and diode drop respectively (Robert & Louis, 1982). The light from the Infrared light emitting diode passes through the slots and incident on the photo sensor base that operates the phototransistor with a reference voltage of

$$V_{ref} = \frac{R_4}{R_3 + R_4} V_{cc} \quad (3)$$

Fig.2: Relationship between Angular Speed (rpm) and Frequency (Hz)

Table1: Cost Analysis

The complete list of the components used in the design of the model of the incremental shaft encoder are enumerated below;

Component	Quantity	Unit price (₦)	Total (₦)
Transformer 240/220V	1	400	400
Diode IN4001	8	15	120
555 timer	1	60	60
UA741 comparator	1	60	60
Counter (4510)	4	150	600
Decoder (4511)	4	150	600
Display	4	150	600
IC Socket (16 pins)	10	25	250
D flip-flop	1	100	100
Quard NAND Schmitt trigger	1	100	100
IC socket (8 pins)	2	20	40
Connecting wires	-	100	100
IC voltage regulator	2	50	100
dc Motor	1	200	200
LED	4	10	40
IR LED	1	120	120
Photo transistor	1	150	150
Zener diode (5V)	1	10	10
Capacitor 220µF, 50V	1	70	70
Total	-	-	3,700

And input voltage of

$$V_{in} = \frac{R_2}{R_2 + R_4} V_{cc} \tag{4}$$

Where V_{ref} and V_{in} are the reference and input voltage respectively (Paul & Windfield, 2001) as shown in Fig.2. These voltages make the photo sensor to conducts offers low resistance/low voltage at the non inverting terminals of the comparator, the comparator then compares the reference voltage and the input voltage to generate a LOW pulse; when the light does not strikes the photo sensor base, the photo sensor does not conducts and offers high resistance/high voltage at the non-inverting terminal of the comparator then a HIGH pulse is generated. The trains of pulse generated at the output of the comparator depends on the frequency/speed in rpm of the shaft. A 555 timer used in this design is configured as astable multi-vibrator that generate a gating pulse of constant time duration (ΔT) of 4s which serves as the means of opening and closing of the logic gate (AND gate) for the trains of the pulse coming from the output of the comparator to be counted by the counter. The period when the gating pulse is HIGH is given by (Green, 2003)

$$T_1 = \ln 2 (R_5 + R_6) C_1 \tag{5}$$

While the period when the gating pulse is LOW is also given by

$$T_2 = \ln 2 R_6 C_1 \tag{6}$$

Then the total time required for trains of pulse to be counted is given by (Ronald & Neal, 2001).

$$T = T_1 + T_2 \tag{7}$$

Table 2: Result of performance and frequency analysis after test

Test	Speed (rpm)	Frequency (Hz)
1	250	63
2	500	125
3	750	188
4	1000	250
5	1250	313
6	1500	378
7	1750	478
8	2000	500
9	2250	563
10	2500	625

And frequency of the oscillation is also determined using (Millman, 1998).

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{T} \tag{8}$$

The frequency required to the reset counting process is given by (Jacob, 1986).

$$f_2 = \frac{1}{2\pi R_7 C_3} \tag{9}$$

Design Procedures

The design takes the following steps

Disc Design

Consider the disc in Fig.3; the slots are drilled at regular interval of 24°

Fig.3: Plastic disc

Let X be the speed in rpm. The number of pulse generated per minute depends on the number of slots in the disc. Since there are 15 slots in the disc we have 15X pulse per minute, one minutes is equal to 60 seconds; Therefore 15X pulses per 60s

$$\frac{15X}{60} = \frac{X}{4}$$

This means that a clock pulse will come in every 4s

Transmitter circuit (IR LED) Design

Fig.4: Transmitter circuit of IR LED

Assume that $I_d = 20\text{mA}$ and $V_d = 2\text{V}$

R_1 was obtained from equation (2) as $R_1 = 333\Omega$, for practical purpose the value of R_1 was chosen from the data as 330Ω as the nearest value.

Receiver and comparator circuit Design

Fig.5 Receiver & comparator circuit

R_3 was set to 100Ω and R_4 was chosen from data book as $1\text{k}\Omega$, the reference voltage was determined as 11V from Equation (3). For the value of R_2 the reference voltage was made approximately closed to the input voltage as 11.8V ($V_{in} \approx V_{cc}$) and R_2 was obtained from Equation (4) as 2240Ω but for practical convenience R_2 was chosen from data book as $2.2\text{k}\Omega$ as the nearest value.

Time base (555 timer) Design

From the disc design $T_1=4s$

Fig. 6: Time base circuit

From Equation (5); when the gating is HIGH, R_5 was determined as $20,028\Omega$ with R_6 and C_1 chosen from data book as $1k\Omega$ and $220\mu f$ respectively. R_5 was also chosen as $20k\Omega$ from data as the next available value. The period when the gating pulse is LOW was determined using Equation (6) as $0.15s$ while the total time when the gating period is HIGH or LOW was determined from Equation (7) as $4.15s$, then the frequency of oscillation was also obtained from Equation (8) as $0.24Hz$.

Control logic circuit (Differentiator) Design

Fig.7: Control logic circuit

The frequency of the oscillation is equal to the frequency required to reset the counting process, this was computed as $0.24Hz$, and the value of C_3 was obtained as $33.02 \times 10^{-9}F$, but C_3 was chosen from the data as $33\mu F$ as the next preferred value

Power Supply Unit

The power supply used in this design incorporate two integrated circuits regulator, which have fixed voltage regulators producing $+5V$ and $+12V$. The transformer is a $240V$ ac input and $24V, 12V$ output. The rectifier is a full wave bridge, which makes use of four rectifier diodes of required rating. The output of the ac voltage is filtered by $50V, 220\mu F$ capacitor and fall to the input of the regulator. The $12V$ regulator

makes use of the KA7812 regulator via 50V, 10 μ F smoothing capacitor, the 12V is further passed through a KA7805 regulator to produce +5V regulated output and 1 μ F capacitor are used to removed any ripple in the design from the regulator that could cause error in the ICs used.

Construction Details

The construction of the circuit did not commence until the circuit was tested on breadboards and found to be working well. The circuit was tested using three breadboards, the counter-decoder units was mounted on the breadboard, a 555 timer was configured as an oscillator and used to check the working of the counters and the decoders.

The comparator stage was also connected on the breadboard and tested for proper functioning; a little adjustment was made on the variable resistor before the circuit could respond to the infrared rays from the infrared LED, the time base differentiator and bubble resolver stage and AND gate that is the control units was also connected and checked for proper functioning. After this preliminary test, all were transferred to the Vero board.

The power supply circuit, the control unit, the time base, the comparator circuit were all housed in one Vero board. During the construction of this stage LED's were used to monitor the output of the time base, the comparator's output and also of the power stage. The seven segment displays were all mounted on one Vero board.

The disc used on the motor shaft was cut to shape with a diameter of 80mm, the 15 slots were then marked out with compass and protractor, the angular spacing of the slots is 24⁰C. The holes in the disc were drilled with the aid of a 4mm drill bit using the drilling machine in the machine laboratory.

Cost Estimate

The designed developed incremental shaft encoder cost (N3, 700.00) which is three times less than the market price of the imported price. If accepted in Nigerian industries, it would tremendously solve the problems of importation.

Performance Testing and Results

The time base unit was calibrated to give precisely a gating duration of 4 seconds. The signal generator in the laboratory was set to a frequency of 250Hz(square wave) and the gating pulse duration was adjusted with the help of the adjustable resistor in the time base unit until it gave a reading of 1000rpm. To further confirm accuracy of the calibration, the frequency was increase to 500Hz and the incremental shaft encoder gave a reading of 2000rpm. To ascertain the relationship between frequency and speed, test of speed verse frequency was carried out, the result is shown in Table 1.

Fig.2 described fully the relationship between the angular seed (rpm) and frequency in (Hz) as the speed increase the frequency also increases.

DISCUSSION

The circuit designed as earlier stated is a prototype of an industrial incremental shaft encoder, which be employed in the field of electrical and electronic instrumentation in Nigeria industries. The imported industrial incremental shaft encoder are very expensive, if this designed is developed and used it will cost many time less than the ones imported. Incremental shaft encoder is hardly used in Nigeria industries except in a vital unit of operations where they become indispensable.

The design used throughout the CMDS version of integrated circuits because mixing it up with other family will definitely requires an interface which would be another design problem to tackle. The TTL, ECL logic family were avoided because of incompatibility with the CMDs circuitry. From test results, this circuit is functional, cheap and simple to maintain.

CONCLUSION

Digital instrument like an incremental shaft encoder used digital method and circuitry with numerical readouts. Some of the transducers commonly encountered in the modern electronic instrumentation gives output signal suitable for direct processing. The digital methods have been popularized in areas of data acquisition, processing and display of availability of inexpensive digital integrated circuits, microprocessor and digital counters.

The aim and objectives of this work has been practically achieved using experimental techniques in electronic engineering, if this design would be accepted in Nigeria in no distant time, an incremental shaft encoder will be as common as any other digital instrument. But the performance of the circuit could be improved by the various techniques such as:

Incorporate programmable speed window to detect and indicate over or under speed of the motor or generator shaft.

Replace UA741 comparator with a very fast response device such as NE527 at several thousand volts per microsecond.

Increase the number of slots in the disc to improve the sensitivity of the circuit.

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